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ORCHESTRA

**Open Architecture and Spatial Data Infrastructure for
Risk Management**

Integrated Project

Priority 2.3.2.9 Improving Risk Management

D3.6.4

OA Services Implementation Version IV

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Revision History

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1.0	2008-02-08	all	1 st public release

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1 **Management Summary**

During the last phase of WP3.6 the available implementation specifications have been continuously improved and adapted to the new template.

A refinement of the service implementation template was required to ensure the consistency to the refined specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform.

2 **Introduction**

2.1 **Purpose and Scope**

This document defines platform-specific OA service specifications, according to the service implementation specification template and the specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform.

This is the fourth deliverable of WP3.6 and contains the final implementation specifications of the following OA Services:

- Annotation Service
- Authentication Service
- Authorisation Service
- Catalogue Service
- Coordinate Operation Service
- Feature Access Service
- Map and Diagram Service
- OA Basic Service
- Ontology Access Service
- Schema Mapping Service
- Service Chain Access Service
- Service Monitoring Service
- User Management Service
- Translating Feature Access Service

2.2 **References**

2.2.1 **Documents and Books**

ORCH-DoW (2007). Integrated Project 511678 ORCHESTRA: “Annex 1 – Description of Work RE-PLANNING AFTER YEAR 2”. 6th Framework Programme IST Priority 2.3.2.9 Improving Risk Management. 10 August 2007

RM-OA (2008) Usländer, T. (Ed.) Reference Model for the ORCHESTRA Architecture Version 3 (Rev. 3.1). Deliverable D3.2.3 of the ORCHESTRA Consortium. http://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=26448. January 2008

ORCH-ImplTemplate (2008) Dihé, P. Template for the implementation Specification of ORCHESTRA

Services. https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=26553. January 2008

ORCH-Platform (2008) Dihé, P. (Ed.) Specification of the ORCHESTRA Web Services Platform. https://portal.opengeospatial.org/files/?artifact_id=26552. January 2008

3 **Service Specifications**

The template, the platform specification, the implementation specifications and the implementations can be found on the ORCHESTRA website <http://www.eu-orchestra.org/> and on the OGC Portal in the folder D3.6.4 - OA Services Implementation Version IV:

https://portal.opengeospatial.org/index.php?m=projects&a=view&project_id=140&tab=2&artifact_id=22247

OA Service	Contributor	Version	Template	Last update
Annotation	IITB	0.2	1.1	2007-04-25
Authentication	EIG	0.8	1.3	2006-12-18
Authorisation	EIG	0.8	1.3	2007-01-28
Catalogue	IITB	0.9	1.1	2007-10-24
Coordinate Operation	ATOS	1.1	1.1	2007-02-28
Feature Access	ARCS	0.3	1.1	2006-12-13
Map and Diagram	ETHZ	1.3	1.1	2007-02-20
OA Basic Service	IITB	0.2	1.1	2006-09-14
Ontology Access	ETHZ	1.0	1.1	2007-02-23
Schema Mapping	JRC-IES	1.0	1.3	2008-01-30
Service Chain Access	JRC-IES	0.2	1.3	2008-02-08
Service Monitoring	ARCS	0.1	1.1	2007-02-26
User Management	EIG	0.8	1.3	2007-01-28
Translating Feature Access Service	JRC-IES	0.4	1.3	2008-01-07

Table 1: OA Service Implementation Specifications